

ALISHER NAVOI IS THE FOUNDER OF THE UZBEK LITERARY LANGUAGE AND PUSHKIN IS THE FOUNDER OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE. COMPARISON OF TWO GREAT PERSONALITIES

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Abstract. *The article considers a comparative analysis of the creativity of the theme of love by Alexander Sergeevich Pushkin and Alisher Navoi, which occupies a significant place. Love inspires and inspires a person, encourages him to create, to move forward. In the lyrics, this topic develops most widely. All poets devoted their poems to the love theme, because it is in the love lyrics that the soul of the poet is most fully revealed. Pushkin and Navoi considered love as a transitory feeling, which, like a wave, covers, captures the poet, gives inspiration and joy, but at the same time quickly departs, leaving only a trace behind. Poets in their poems deify women, praise their beautiful qualities.*

Keywords: *A.Pushkin, A.Navoi, love, poet, lyrics, idea.*

INTRODUCTION

The soul has been of interest to the cognizing humanity throughout its history in many ways, which was naturally expressed in the variety of directions and forms of its research. In various epochs, the main sources of the latter were both religious attitudes, empirical data reflecting the connection of the soul and body, and the results of speculative observations by a person of the mental processes taking place in himself. One of the essential features of the medieval period of the evolution of psychological knowledge is precisely the assertion of the unity of the designated sources. [1]

The theme of love is one of the eternal themes, one of the most beautiful themes, so A.S. Pushkin and A.Navoi could not get around it in anyway, so they turned to it both in their youth and in a more mature period.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Alisher Navoi, a poet and philosopher of the Sufi trend, highly valued science and the human mind and considered wisdom and knowledge to be the adornments of man. In his works, the issues of education and upbringing are very widely disclosed, and his pedagogical views are deeply humanistic. He paid great attention to the issues of raising a child, who for Navoi was a luminary in the house, bringing happiness and joy to the family. Navoi condemned coercive teaching methods both at school and at home, speaking out against corporal punishment. He considered ignorant teachers to be a punishment for the school, because the teacher is obliged to know the subject taught by him perfectly, understand the needs of the people, have deep knowledge and set an example in everything. Navoi urged teachers to instill in students love for the motherland and respect for the most valuable and highest gift of the universe – man. [5]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Issues of labor and moral education occupy a significant place in the poet's works. He was ahead of his time by many centuries, his brilliant works, thoughts and ideas had a huge impact on

the development of scientific thought and spiritual life of the Uzbek and other peoples of Central Asia in the historical era of the Eastern Renaissance. Despite the past centuries, his creative heritage, which is a treasure trove of world significance, remains for new generations an inexhaustible storehouse of wisdom and humanistic knowledge of the surrounding world.

Our greatest ancestor – poet, thinker and statesman Alisher Navoi was an outstanding personality who amazed both contemporaries and us, descendants, with the diversity and versatility of his interests and talents, a great desire to penetrate the secrets and secrets of science, art and crafts. [6]

Love, according to Navoi, is a very strong feeling, a primary feeling born with a person, incongruous and incommensurable. But love is never alone. She is always accompanied by feelings such as hatred and loneliness. Love cannot even ask God for help, because God is hostile to love, does not accept it, denies it. Therefore, love lyrics are the lyrics of suffering, laments and curses. Alisher Navoi's love lyrics are characterized by biographism and cyclization. In the poems, one can trace the stages of love: its origin, development, rise, decline, termination. [7]

Alisher Navoi is a singer of love and the joys of life. Often in the poet's gazelles there is an image of wine, symbolizing the love of life and optimism of the lyrical hero's life views. Navoi opposes rinda to pessimists, sheikhs, ascetics. [8]

The leading theme of Navoi's lyrics was love in a variety of manifestations. In lyrical poems, as in other works of the poet, we find the ideas of a great, exciting love, full of self-denial and self-sacrifice, ideal, pure love. This is, first of all, love for a woman, but not only. This is also love for close people, love for the Motherland, for people in general, because a person is the pearl of life. But only noble, morally pure people are capable of great true love. And only then is love capable of great things: [7]

A fool was scaring me: the world will perish!

The world will be resurrected by the hand of love. And he will call the love of people to a feast,

Where the king and the beggar drink the infusion of love. Under her cloud they are equal, washed from sins by the river of love.

And even the light descends on the hypocrites – What for? – they can't understand such love.

The theme of love in Pushkin's lyrics in different periods of his work is revealed to him in different ways. During the lyceum period, this is an easy, frivolous feeling, one of the pleasures of life. In the Petersburg period, love is connected with the patriotic aspirations of the poet: it is love for the Motherland. During the period of southern exile, Pushkin portrays love as a romantic, devastating passion. And only in Mikhailovsky Pushkin comes to understand love as the highest value of a person. Love is now connected with his inner freedom, which can awaken inspiration and the best human feelings in the poet. [1]

A.S. Pushkin's poems were dedicated to many women. However, it is possible to distinguish several common motives in the poet's love lyrics:

- love as a carefree pleasure, an easy, pleasant feeling (lyceum period);
- love is a deep, dramatic passion (southern link);
- perfect, eternal feeling;
- love is the source of inner freedom;

Researchers of Pushkin's creativity considered that he dedicated poems to one hundred and thirty-seven women. These hobbies, the constant feeling of falling in love helped him to create beautiful works. [2]

Love is the force that determines the existence of human life. Pushkin had his own idea of love, and talked about it in his works. His lyrics are filled with the beauty of life, the beauty of feelings. Each of his poems is a piece of his soul, which he exposes to readers and, of course, to his Beautiful Lady. Speaking about how the theme of love is revealed in Pushkin's lyrics, it is worth saying that it is rich in images, many faces. Pushkin knew how to love, appreciated the feeling of love. The feeling of love is manifested in Pushkin's poems very gracefully and deeply. [3]

Belinsky noted that the poet's high feeling is not limited only to experiences, his other qualities, an artist and an artist, were embodied here. All the poet's lyrics are a novel in verse, the main subject of which is the inner world of the hero, his experiences, sorrows and joys. During his short life, the poet created many beautiful poems and works. His poems are devoted to various subjects. There are poems dedicated to philosophy, friendship, freedom, but the most beautiful were the poems and the magical feeling of love. His poems are light and swift in form, his love lyrics are diverse and rich. [4]

Lightness is the main thing that we notice from his works in the form of the very first and basic feeling. "Pushkin's lightness was also in relation to life, it was the basis of Pushkin's worldview, a feature of his character and biography." In the first poems, one could notice the lightness in the verse. Critics admired the lightness and smoothness of his poems, as if "they were not worth any work, as if they poured out of him by themselves. Konstantin Balmont said that "Pushkin is the sun of Russian poetry, which spread its rays over a vast distance and brought to life an infinite number of large and small satellites." [2]

Pushkin is not limited only to changing the form of his works. He offers the reader a completely new system of values. Everything here is based on respect for the subject of sighs. The poet, with his characteristic worldly wisdom, proves that the beloved also has the right to choose. Even if the feelings turn out to be unrequited, this does not mean at all that you need to challenge your lucky opponent to a duel. The poet does not spare words to show the power of his love.

I remember a wonderful moment:

You appeared before me, Like a fleeting vision,
Like a genius of pure beauty.

Only love can brighten up a sad and sad life, be a consolation and happiness. The soul has awakened:

And here you are again, Like a fleeting vision,

Like a genius of pure beauty. And the heart beats in ecstasy, And for him they were resurrected again

Both divinity and inspiration, And life, and tears, and love.

Pushkin was able to describe the excitement that a lover feels, his experiences. The reader feels the suffering of the hero, the strength of his love, sympathizes with the hero and rejoices for him. Pushkin's poems help to understand that love is the strongest and brightest feeling, that it is necessary to love a loved one strongly and unresponsively, to understand and respect him. The whole gamut of human feelings is reflected in the poet's poems: the bitterness of love and the joy of love, the happiness of falling in love, the fear of losing a loved one.

CONCLUSION

Comparing the love lyrics of A.S. Pushkin and A.Navoi, we can conclude that their love experiences are very similar. Each of the poets experiences certain life difficulties, which, one way or another, affect the development of lyrics. Both poets are now disappointed in love, then full of it again. This feeling completely captures them. Hence the similarity of themes and motives of their love lyrics.

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